

SOCIAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF FAMILY INFLUENCE IN THE PROFESSIONAL CHOICE PROCESS IN THE EXAMPLE OF SCHOOL PUPILS

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Annotation: This article analyzes the influence of the family factor on the lives of schoolchildren in the process of choosing a profession from a social and psychological perspective. The study covers the family environment, the role of parents in career guidance, and the main factors influencing children's professional interests and inclinations. It also examines how psychological processes in choosing a profession, family values, and parents' ideal professional visions affect students' decisions to choose a profession. The article is written based on practical observations and analysis on the example of schoolchildren, which helps to better understand the importance of the family in the career guidance of young people.

Keywords: Career choice, family influence, schoolchildren, social analysis, psychological processes, parental role, professional interest, family values, professional guidance

1 INTRODUCTION

Choosing which of the many professions to choose, knowing whether it matches one's inclinations, abilities and interests, is of great importance in the individual's perspective. In particular, guiding young students to a profession is an integral part of the work of a general education school. It is known that if a profession is chosen correctly, work becomes a source of joy and creative inspiration for a person, which is beneficial for both the individual and society. In this regard, as our psychologists emphasize, a person's free choice of what he wants is of great importance. When a person is engaged in a job he loves, he can be happy with this work, gain satisfaction, show a lot of initiative, and work tirelessly and enthusiastically. In order to thoroughly prepare young people for independent work and to ensure that they choose the right profession according to their abilities, it is necessary for school teachers to have high pedagogical skills, knowledge level, and didactic abilities, to study the basics of science in connection with life, to organize clubs and additional, auxiliary courses rationally, to give lectures on professions in schools, to hold conversations, discussions, organize trips, meetings, and professional photo exhibitions. Creating interest in the profession is directly related to the teacher's pedagogical activity.

2 METHODS AND MATERIALS

Linking labor education with life, harmonizing it, taking into account the individual typological and age characteristics of students, technical abilities, intellectual levels and capabilities will have a positive effect. Because each profession requires a person to exert willpower, mental seriousness and withstand tests, only those boys and girls who can be considered suitable for this chosen profession. Before directing a student to a particular profession, it is necessary to study his personality. For this, it is possible to observe him, analyze the student's practical actions at school, in public places, in the family and at work, conduct a questionnaire, interview, test, etc. In order to rationally organize the activity of choosing a profession, it is necessary to take into account which areas of specialization our country needs and, accordingly, to select schoolchildren based on their inclinations, aspirations, interests, opportunities, mental and physical abilities, as well as determine their suitability for this or that profession, and then send them to the profession. In career guidance, it is of great importance to

provide students with information about various professions, the requirements for them, and where they can acquire these skills.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The development of professional skills and human thinking, the ability to see existing problems in science and ways to solve them, all this is a problematic-heuristic level. Here we will consider the theoretical and practical aspects of the professional orientation of students:

- the theoretical aspect of career guidance involves the formation of in-depth knowledge of all aspects of professional activity, education based on this knowledge, the application of theoretical knowledge to practice and, conversely, the study of ways to transfer practice to theory.

- the practical aspect of career guidance involves learning to apply the acquired knowledge in a specific area of life. This prepares young people to be conscious of choosing a profession. Students can learn information and knowledge about professions not only at school, but also from the media, acquaintances, and relatives. Taking into account the above, when directing young people to a profession, it is necessary to pay attention to the following:

- timely determination of students' activity, hobbies, aspirations, desires, motives, good intentions, and interest in a particular profession.

- rationally directing each of them to a profession, taking into account the individual typological characteristics, age and gender of students;

- in order to rationally organize the activity of choosing a profession, it is necessary to consider which field of specialists our country needs and, accordingly, determine their suitability for a particular profession, depending on their mental and physical abilities, and then direct them to a profession; - establish strong ties with parents; - it is necessary to organize consultations on career guidance. Career guidance of young people is a well-founded system of socio-economic, psychological, pedagogical, medical-biological and production-technical measures aimed at helping young people to determine their future profession. The content of youth work is determined on the basis of the social, political and economic tasks facing the country, the need for personnel in the regions and districts, the internal capabilities and requirements of educational institutions. Vocational guidance is understood as a complex of psychological, pedagogical, and medical measures aimed at optimizing the process of placing young people in work in accordance with their desires and formed abilities, as well as taking into account the needs of the national economy and society as a whole for specialists. Organization of vocational guidance of schoolchildren in general secondary educational institutions, the formation of professional knowledge and motivation in students, adaptation to the professional world in social life and skills of teamwork are one of the urgent problems of our time. The main goal of assisting schoolchildren in choosing a profession is to organize career guidance work in general secondary educational institutions, to form professional knowledge and motivation in students, skills for adapting to the professional world in social life, and skills for teamwork. The school psychologist is responsible for developing:

- to expand students' ideas about professions, to teach them to apply their abilities and capabilities in practice;

- to form students' cognitive motivations, develop their intellectual and creative abilities, and expand their ideas about the world of professions; - to teach students to study their own abilities in relation to the profession, develop their creative abilities, and teach them to work with reference books and encyclopedic literature; - to continuously guide students to the profession, identify and guide their professional interests, abilities, inclinations, and abilities from an early age based on psychological and pedagogical diagnostic methods;

- to conduct promotional activities involving parents and the general public in guiding students to the profession. In order to study the professional aptitude of students, it is necessary to know their

mental and physical abilities, skills, and abilities. Creating interest in the profession is directly related to the teacher's pedagogical activity. Linking and harmonizing vocational education with life, taking into account the individual and typological, age characteristics, technical abilities, intellectual levels, and capabilities of students will have a positive effect. Because each profession requires willpower, mental seriousness, and the ability to withstand trials, only those students who are able to withstand the chosen profession are considered suitable for the chosen profession.

4 CONCLUSION

The process of choosing a profession plays an important role not only in economic life, but also in the spiritual and social development of a person. Therefore, it is necessary to form a readiness in students to consciously determine their professional path from school. Psychological counseling, professional diagnostics, tests and interviews aimed at identifying the individual characteristics and interests of students are of great importance within the framework of professional selection. In this regard, cooperation between the family and the school plays a special role. The advice and support that parents give their children regarding their choice of profession have a positive effect on students' independent decision-making. At the same time, it is also necessary to provide parents with knowledge in the field of professional orientation and help them correctly assess the abilities and inclinations of their children. In the conditions of the modern labor market, students should be provided with comprehensive information about modern professions, innovative technologies and labor requirements when choosing a profession. For this purpose, it is useful to organize professional exhibitions, meetings with specialists, and excursions to industrial enterprises in schools. Through this, students will not only gain theoretical knowledge, but also get acquainted with real working conditions and more clearly understand their interests and capabilities. When making a professional choice, it is also important to develop students' skills such as social activity, communication culture, teamwork skills, and stress tolerance. Therefore, educational work on choosing a profession should not be limited only to providing information about professions, but should also be aimed at developing personal and social competencies. In addition, early identification of students' professional interests and inclinations with the help of psychological services and offering them individual development directions increases efficiency. Using special diagnostic methods, the student's professional abilities are identified and specific recommendations for their development are developed. In conclusion, the issue of choosing a profession for schoolchildren is a multifaceted, complex and responsible process, and work in this area should be carried out systematically, goal-oriented and based on an individual approach to the person. Only when the joint efforts of school, family, and society are harmoniously directed towards the process of choosing a career will students be able to find their place in life and achieve professional success.

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